

Analysis of Inter-community coordination strategies and the impact on energy communities

Josh Eichman, Mariana Jiménez Martínez, Cristina Corchero

Motivation

- European energy goals seek to **reduce consumption, increase efficiency and increase renewable shares.**
- **Energy communities** can help to address the European goals
- **Clean Energy for All Europeans Package (CEP)** creates a framework for energy communities, amongst other things
- Expansion of **Spanish framework** for energy communities and **incentives**
 - RD 477/2021: €1.12 billion for self-consumption and storage
- Limited literature comparing community coordination strategies including **Collective Self-Consumption (CSC)** in Spain
- Current literature does not include recent **updates to CSC rules** in Spain
 - Hourly variable distribution coefficient

Methodology

1. Load Only
2. Load + PV
(no export)
3. Load + PV
(with export)
4. Load + PV + Batt.
(no export)
5. Load + PV + Batt.
(with export)

Scenarios include:

- CSC (with and w/o)
- Export (with and w/o)
- 5 retail rates (see backup for details)
- 2 locations (see backup for details)
- 2 sizes (see backup for details)

Item	Device configurations	Collective self-consumption	Renewable sales	Retail Rates	Location	Size
1	Load only	Yes, No	Yes, No	5	Distributed, centralized	Large, Small
2	Load + PV	Yes, No	Yes, No	5	Distributed, centralized	Large, Small
3	Load + PV + Battery	Yes, No	Yes, No	5	Distributed, centralized	Large, Small

Device assumptions

Parameter	Value
PV capital cost	\$1387/kW [1]
PV fixed operation & maintenance cost	\$10/kW-year [1]
Storage capital cost	\$955/kWh [1]
Storage energy capacity	4 hours at rated discharge power
Storage efficiency	85% AC to AC
Storage self-discharge	1% of stored energy per day [2]

Financial assumptions

Parameter	Value
Euro to dollar	0.89
Study period	20 years
Tax rate	25%
Equity	41.9%
Interest rate on debt	3.125% [3]
Inflation	1.6%
WACC	7%
Depreciation schedule	10% for up to 20 years [4]

1. IRENA, "Renewable Power Generation Costs in 2020," International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi, 2021.
2. E. Redondo-Iglesias, P. Venet, and S. Pelissier, "Measuring Reversible and Irreversible Capacity Losses on Lithium-Ion Batteries," in 2016 IEEE Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conference (VPPC), Hangzhou, China, Oct. 2016, pp. 1–5. doi: 10.1109/VPPC.2016.7791723.
3. Banco de España, "Table of banks' lending and borrowing rates." https://clientebancario.bde.es/pcb/en/menu-horizontal/productoservici/relacionados/tiposinteres/guia-textual/tiposinteresprac/Tabla_de_tipos__a0b053c69a40f51.html.
4. infoautónomos, "¿Qué son las amortizaciones? ¿Cómo funcionan? Ejemplo." <https://www.infoautonomos.com/contabilidad/tablas-de-amortizacion-para-los-bienes-de-una-empresa/>.

Community description

- The community is comprised of 8 members (see backup for details)
- Location is based on Barcelona, Spain.
- Data is developed using the LoadProfileGenerator†

† Noah Pflugradt, *LoadProfileGenerator*. 2022. [Online]. <https://www.loadprofilegenerator.de/>

#	Identifier (CHR)	Description	Max. Power (kW)	Min. Power (kW)	Avg. Power (kW)	StDev of Power (kW)
1	01	Couple both at work	6.59	0.103	0.617	0.792
2	05	Family with 3 children, both parents work	3.76	0.045	0.594	0.589
3	07	Working single person	3.94	0.046	0.205	0.370
4	15	Multigenerational family with 2 working adults, 2 children and 2 seniors	7.82	0.100	1.382	1.233
5	16	Couple over 65 years old	5.49	0.017	0.584	0.795
6	22	Single working woman with 1 child	2.10	0.055	0.213	0.285
7	40	Non-working couple (30-64 years old)	3.00	0.062	0.406	0.439
8	52	Student sharing an apartment	4.08	0.052	0.426	0.489

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Applications

- Multi-market optimization
- Hydrogen business case assessment
- Wholesale market revenue comparison
- Retail rate optimization
- Solar PV + Storage
- Real-time optimization control of electrolyzer
- Vehicle fleet optimization

Results

- CSC with export is the least cost
- Generally, CSC (no export) is better than SC with export.
- Large systems were preferred
- Distributed systems have lower operating cost than concentrated systems

CSC: Collective self-consumption
 SC: Individual self-consumption

Dist.: Distributed
 Cocen.: Concentrated

Results

- Allowing export is the most effective way to reduce curtailment
- For CSC without export there can be a tradeoff between NPV and curtailment

Collective self-consumption		Yes	Yes	No	No
Sale of renewables		Yes	No	Yes	No
NPV (thousand €)	PV	-116	-123	-129	-142
	PV + Battery	-121	-122	-130	-144
Curtailment (MWh)	PV	0.0	5.7	0.0	11.1
	PV + Battery	0.0	1.3	0.0	6.4

Next steps

- Demonstrate the ability to control real CSC systems
- Expand the load scenarios to characterize more types of communities.
- Explore the impact of optimization under uncertainty (PV forecasting, energy limited storage, etc.)

Thank you for your attention

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Josh Eichman (jeichman@irec.cat)

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Device and Financial assumptions

Device assumptions

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Storage efficiency	85% AC to AC
Storage self-discharge	1% of stored energy per day [2]
Retail electricity rates	Sale price based on wholesale market price [3] Endesa (One Luz and One Luz 3 period) [4,5] Hola Luz (Classic and Fair rate) [6] Pepe Energy (ECO) [7]

Financial assumptions

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Sizing and location breakdown

- PV size for small systems is based on 75% of average load at site
- PV size for large systems is based on 50% of max. load at site
- Storage size for small systems is based on 20% of average load
- Storage size for large systems is based on 20% of max load at site

PV sizing and location

Location	Size	Consumer							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Distributed	Small	0.5	0.4	0.2	1.0	0.4	0.2	0.3	0.3
Concentrated	Small		1.6	1.7					
Distributed	Large	3.3	1.9	2.0	3.9	2.7	1.1	1.5	2.0
Concentrated	Large		9.0	9.4					

Storage sizing and location

Location	Size	Consumer							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Distributed	Small	0.12	0.1	0.0	0.28	0.12	0.04	0.08	0.09
Concentrated	Small		0.4	0.5					
Distributed	Large	1.3	0.8	0.8	1.6	1.1	0.4	0.6	0.8
Concentrated	Large		3.6	3.8					